

EDUCATION 4.0: TEACHERS' KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES, BELIEFS AND INSTRUCTIONAL PRACTICES

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Abstract:

In education, significant changes were noted from lectures and memorization in Education 1.0, internet-enabled learning in Education 2.0, knowledge-producing education in Education 3.0, then to innovative-producing education in Education 4.0. With the changes in education, this study is conducted to determine the extent of teachers' knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, and instructional practices in the context of Education 4.0. A quantitative descriptive research design using survey technique was employed. The participants of this study were the higher education faculty of St. Paul University System. The main instrument that was used to solicit for information is a researcher-made questionnaire consisting of five (5) parts. Mean and Standard Deviation, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, and Multiple Linear Regression Analysis were the statistical tools used in this study. The results showed a positive relationship among the knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes towards Education 4.0. It is further revealed that attitude is significantly correlated to instructional practices. Recommendations are hereby given to address the needs and demands of the Fourth Industrial Revolution in Education.

Keywords: Education 4.0, knowledge, beliefs, attitude, instructional practices

INTRODUCTION

Evolution today is taking place at an accelerated pace as change is now measured in years and not centuries. In education, significant changes were noted from lectures and memorization in Education 1.0, internet-enabled learning in Education 2.0, and knowledge-producing education in Education 3.0.

Today, we are again at the point of a change where the learner will be at the center of the future ecosystem in Education 4.0, which focuses on innovative-producing education. Education 4.0 empowers learners to structure their learning paths. It is characterized by personalization of the learning experience. The learner has complete flexibility to be the architect of his or her future and has the freedom to aspire, approach, and achieve personal goals by choice (FICCI Higher Education Committee, 2017).

In addition, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (2019), mentioned that the biggest threat to our school systems today is not that they are ineffective or inefficient, it becomes obsolete because the world requires a diverse set of skills.

Moreover, Fisk (2017) mentioned that there are trends in Education 4.0 that should be put into practice. These trends will address the need to provide a personalized learning environment

to the learners. Personalized learning involves creating a flexible time where learners can learn anytime and anywhere.

With the changes and challenges brought about by the Fourth Industrial Revolution in Education, the researcher conducted a study to know the extent of teacher's knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, and instructional practices in the context of Education 4.0. The researcher considered such because Wilkins (2008) mentioned that teachers' knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs play an important role in teachers' effectiveness and their choice of instructional practices. Kutaka et al. (2018) also found out that mathematical knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes are not only influenced by one another—they also affect instruction in complex ways.

This study aims to determine the extent of teachers' knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, and instructional practices in the context of Education 4.0. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following: extent of teachers' knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs about Education 4.0; extent of instructional practices of the teachers aligned to the thrusts of Education 4.0; relationship among the teachers' knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs about Education 4.0; and relationship between the extent of teachers' knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs about Education 4.0 and their instructional practices.

As St. Paul University Surigao moves towards addressing the Fourth Industrial Revolution, the findings will give an idea to the university as to how members of the St. Paul University System work towards Education 4.0. The findings will also serve as an additional basis for future projects to be implemented by the university.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey research design was used in this study to allow the researcher to gather more precise and quantifiable information on the extent of knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs towards Education 4.0 of the teachers from the member schools of the St. Paul University System, Academic Year 2019-2020. The design was deemed appropriate because this is probably the best method that is available to use in collecting data for the abovementioned purpose.

The participants of this study were the teachers of the member schools of the St. Paul University System. This system is composed of: St. Paul University Philippines, St. Paul University Manila, St. Paul University Quezon City, St. Paul University Iloilo, St. Paul University Dumaguete and St. Paul University Surigao. Random sampling was employed in gathering data. There were 79 participants who responded and answered the survey questionnaire.

The main instrument used to solicit for information was a researcher-made questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of five (5) parts. Part 1 is on the respondents' profile, which includes age, sex, years of service, and highest educational attainment. Part 2 is on the extent of knowledge on Education 4.0. Part 3 contains the indicators on the attitude about Education 4.0. Part 4 consists of the beliefs about Education 4.0. Part 5 deals with instructional practices in the context of Education 4.0.

The questionnaire was subjected to content validation of experts and reliability tests. The Cronbach alpha (α) obtained was 0.9094 which means that there is an excellent internal consistency.

In determining the extent of knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, and instructional practices in the context of Education 4.0, Mean and Standard Deviation were used. Moreover, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the relationship among the extent of knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs about Education 4.0 and the instructional practices. Likewise,

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis was used to describe the data and to explain the relationship between one dependent variable (instructional practices) and two or more independent variables (knowledge, attitudes and beliefs).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Perceived Knowledge on Education 4.0

Among the 16 indicators, the item *I am aware that the role of a teacher is a facilitator, coach, and mentor* got the highest mean ($\underline{M}=3.96$, $SD=0.19$), which can be verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly knowledgeable*. This means that the participants knew very well of their role as an educator in the Fourth Industrial Revolution. This is true because, in this era of education, there is a shift in the teacher's role from being a sage on the stage to a guide on the side. Thanh (2018) stated that the value of the teacher is not as lecturers but as a guide, catalyst to help students to orient themselves in learning. Meanwhile, the item *I am aware that education should put premium on mobile learning* got the lowest mean ($\underline{M}=3.30$, $SD=0.69$), which can be verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly knowledgeable*. Despite being the lowest indicator, it still yielded a highly knowledgeable description, which means that the participants are well aware of putting a premium on mobile learning. Fisk (2017) emphasized that e-Learning tools offer great opportunities for remote, self-paced learning. On average, the participants' *perceived knowledge* on Education 4.0 is verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly knowledgeable* ($\underline{M}=3.64$, $SD=0.29$). This means that the participants are fully aware of the nature and demands of the fourth industrial revolution in education.

Attitude towards Education 4.0

Among the 11 indicators, the item *I have the interest and willingness to use the new educational practices* got the highest mean ($\underline{M}=3.82$, $SD=0.42$), which can be verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly valued*. Instructional practices are dynamic. Teachers' attitude towards the updating of practices is very high as it is necessary to address the needs of times as well as to cater to the learning needs of the students in the Fourth Industrial Revolution. However, the item *I have helped others, especially those struggling in practicing the new trends in education* got the lowest mean ($\underline{M}=3.27$, $SD=0.23$), which can be verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly valued*. Despite being the lowest indicator, it still yielded a highly valued description, which means that the participants' attitude towards helping others is very much valued. Teachers are of different generations, which may be one reason why some are struggling to adapt to new trends. While this may be true, Romanes and Veniegas (2018) found out in their study that boomers have greater skills in extending the 21st century skills to their classroom than generations X and Y. On average, the participants' *attitude* towards Education 4.0 is verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly valued* ($\underline{M}=3.64$, $SD=0.31$). This shows that the participants possess a positive attitude towards Education 4.0 as it prepares the learners to become both productive contributors to future economies and responsible and active citizens in future societies.

Beliefs about Education 4.0

Among the 14 indicators, the items *I believe that education empowers learners to structure their learning paths; learning should be learner-centered; learning can take place anytime*

anywhere; the learner constructs his/her knowledge as he/she collaborates with peers and experts; and the learner should possess the complex problem solving, social and process skills to prepare them for real-life situations got the highest means (\underline{M} =3.84, SD =0.37, 0.41, 0.41, 0.41, and 0.37, respectively) which are verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly accepted*. The result agrees with Fisk (2017) that learning is built around the learners as to where and how to learn, highlighting that Education 4.0 is learner-centered and respects students' learning styles. Personalized and self-paced learning, as identified by the WEF (2020) as a critical characteristic of learning content and experiences, moves from a system where learning is standardized, to one based on the diverse individual needs and flexible enough to allow each learner to progress at their own pace.

However, the item *I believe that learning should be the responsibility of the learner* got the lowest mean (\underline{M} =3.34, SD =0.70) is verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly accepted*. It is true that in this era of education, learners work for their learning, and teachers facilitate their learning. Despite being the lowest indicator, the participants still believe that the learners are responsible for their learning. It is the learner who is responsible for defining the various dimensions of his education path — the what, where, when, how and why while moving up the learning ladder (FICCI Higher Education Committee, 2017). On average, the participants' belief about Education 4.0 is verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly accepted* (\underline{M} =3.72, SD =0.31). This means that the participants highly believe in the nature and principles of Education 4.0, where the learner is at the center of the future ecosystem focusing on an innovative-productive education.

Instructional Practices in Education 4.0

Among the 17 instructional practices, the item *I employ hands-on learning in class for better understanding of a concept* got the highest mean (\underline{M} =3.71, SD =0.51), which can be verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly practiced*. This means that the participants use hands-on learning in the delivery of instruction. As defined by Owen (2020), a hands-on learning approach helps students build the skills they need to be career-ready, developing abilities such as problem-solving, teamwork, creativity, and critical thinking.

However, the item *I employ video chatting for collaborative, distant discussion* got the lowest mean (\underline{M} =2.56, SD =0.94), which can be verbally interpreted as *often* and qualitatively described as *practiced*. The teachers often use this practice because one of the barriers to distance education in the Philippines is limited or slow internet connectivity. It is also noted that the items *I employ online courses for self-paced learning of the students* and *I employ flipped classroom approach to allow interactive learning in class* were among the often employed practices by the participants. These practices require internet connectivity to make learning more effective. Salac and Kim's (2016) study shows that the country's internet infrastructure lags among those of contemporary developing countries in Asia, particularly in terms of internet connectivity. On average, the participants' *instructional practices* in Education 4.0 are verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly practiced* (\underline{M} =3.35, SD =0.45).

Relationship among the teachers' knowledge, attitudes and beliefs about Education 4.0

In terms of its relationship among the extent of knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs about Education 4.0, there is a *low positive correlation* between *knowledge* and *attitudes* (r =0.43), while there is a *moderate positive correlation* between *knowledge and beliefs* and *attitudes and beliefs* (r =0.50 and 0.54, respectively). Anderson (2005) found out that teachers' attitudes toward

mathematics can also influence teachers' beliefs. In this study, it was found that there is a *moderate positive correlation* between attitude and beliefs. Moreover, beliefs are also influenced by teachers' knowledge. In Mathematics, teachers with more knowledge are likely to be more confident and less anxious about learning mathematics (Kalder and Lesik, 2011). If one has no beliefs about a particular matter, one cannot have knowledge about it (Truncellito, nd). Knowledge, then, requires belief. Belief is necessary but not sufficient for knowledge. People are mistaken sometimes in what they believe.

Relationship between extent of knowledge, attitudes, beliefs and instructional practices

Correlation and multiple regression analyses were conducted to examine the relationship between the teachers' *knowledge, attitudes and beliefs* and *instructional practices*. Findings revealed the *knowledge, attitudes and beliefs* are positively correlated with the *instructional practices* ($r=0.26, 0.53, \text{ and } 0.38$, respectively). There is a *negligible correlation* between *knowledge* and *instructional practices*, a *low positive correlation* between *beliefs* and *instructional practices*, and a *moderate positive correlation* between *attitudes* and *instructional practices*. Kutaka et al. (2018) found out that knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes are not only influenced by one another—they also affect instruction in complex ways. Ernest's (1989) model posited that knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs are all found to have a direct influence on teachers' instructional practices but not necessarily correlated.

There is no significant relationship between *knowledge and instructional practices* and *beliefs and instructional practices* ($p\text{-values} = 0.920 \text{ and } 0.252$, respectively). The results contradict Palak's (2004) findings, which revealed that teachers' beliefs are the primary agents for their instructional technology decisions specifically for their selections of technologies for student use. Khan (2017) also found out that the instructional beliefs of the teacher educators were significantly correlated with their classroom practices.

However, only the *attitude* poses a significant relationship with *instructional practices* ($p\text{-value}=0.000$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between *attitude* and *instructional practices*. More positive teacher attitudes are associated with success in teaching. Teachers who have positive attitudes can establish good relationships in classes, create positive energy, and facilitate the process of learning, which all enhance the quality of teaching (Sener, 2015). The result further implies that despite having high knowledge and a strong belief in the trends of education, attitude plays a more important role as it significantly contributes to the success of the teaching practices in the Fourth Industrial Revolution in Education. Ahmad et al. (2013) found out that teachers with a positive professional attitude perform better in the teaching and learning process. They are more motivated towards their profession. In any profession, a negative or positive attitude affects the performance and the degree of realization of the goals (Ball and Lampert, 1999).

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings revealed in this study, it is, therefore concluded that St. Paul University System is in Education 4.0, where the teachers are coaches, mentors, and facilitators of learning, and students are at the center of the school system who are exposed to hands-on and experiential activities to create lifelong and student-driven learning. Knowledge and beliefs are non-predictors of instructional practices. Having extensive knowledge and strong beliefs do not ensure the practice of such, but attitudes, whether negative or positive, are drivers of action or practice.

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